

A Critical Study on Business Strategies of TCS Ltd.

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Abstract:

Tata Consultancy Services Limited (TCS) is an Indian multi-national Information Technology (IT) service, consulting company headquartered in Mumbai, Maharashtra state. It is a part of the Tata Group and operates in 46 countries with over four lacks employee. TCS is one of India's largest companies by market capitalization. TCS is now placed among the most valuable IT services brands in the worldwide nation. TCS Limited was founded or organized in 1968 by the division of Tata Sons Limited. TSC had early contracts included punched card services to sister's company TISCO (now Tata Steel), working on an Inter-Branch reconciliation System for the Central Bank of India and providing bureau services to Unit Trust of India. In 1975, TCS delivered a depository electronic and trading system is called SECOM for the Swiss company SIS Segal Inter Settle (Dutch). TCS is also developed System X for the Canadian Depository System and automated the Johannesburg Stock Exchange. It is associated with a Swiss partner, TKS Teknosoft, which it later acquired. In 1980, TCS established India's first dedicated software research and development center, the Tata Research Development and Design Centre (TRDDC) in Pune. In 1981, it established India's first client-dedicated offshore development center, set up for clients Tandem. On 25 August 2004, TCS became a Publicly Listed Company. In 2015, TCS is ranked 64th overall in the Forbes World's Most Innovative Companies ranking, making it both the highest-ranked IT services company and the top Indian company. TCS is the world second largest IT services provider. As of 2017, TCS is also ranked 10th on the Fortune India 500 list. In April 2018, TCS has become the first Indian IT company to reach \$100 billion market capitalization, and second Indian company (after Reliance Industries achieved it in 2007) After its m-cap stood at \$102.6 billion in Bombay Stock Exchange(BSE). TCS and its 67 subsidiaries are provided a wide range of Information Technology-related products and services including application development, business process outsourcing, capacity planning, consulting, enterprise software, hardware sizing, payment processing, technology education services, and software management. The established firm's software products are TCS BaNCS and TCS MasterCraft.

In this paper, we have analyzed the business strategy of TCS by studying its business level strategies including acquisition strategy, operational strategy, services strategy, technology adoption strategy, HR strategy, functional strategy, marketing strategy, and growth strategy. The paper also includes the analysis of a company's strength, weakness, and outlook.

Keyword: TCS, Tata group, Tata Sons Limited, TKS, TRDCC, SECOM, Forbes, Indian IT Company.

1. INTRODUCTION

TCS is a Software engineering and data innovation have swung to be the blasting field of enthusiasm for late years. It is ceaselessly creating and new employment are made in this field each month. Obviously, there is a tremendous challenge for employment in software engineering and data innovation segment. Goodbye Consultancy Services also called TCS is one of the most astounding utilizing organizations over the world. TCS is known to enroll an enormous number of designers from various branches of study. Besides, TCS is a rumored organization and in this manner, everybody needs to get a vocation in TCS. What inconveniences the hopefuls in the meeting technique. The TCS inquiries questions are intended to choose the best among every one of the candidates. Subsequently, it is imperative to become accustomed to the successive inquiries asked in the meeting. TCS organization inquiries questions are not troublesome. By the by, handling the inquiries questions requires quickness and certainty. Subsequently, the oftentimes made inquiries must be polished before going for a genuine meeting. Be that as it may, never rely upon what you have realized, ensure you have enough common sense to answer different inquiries adroitly.

2. OBJECTIVES

- To analyze the overall Growth of the company.
- To find the Services and Products provided by the company.
- To find out the Market Share and business strategies of the company.
- To Check the different Solutions for improving the Growth of the company.

3. SMART PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

TCS offers a variety of specialized engagements from the adoption of roadmaps for smart producing to go-to-market strategies for connected merchandise. There are several factors that go into mounting a successful emissions management program, and there is one company that can help you with all of them – Technical Compliance Solutions (TCS). TCS offer a full range of emissions permitting and testing services to ensure your operation remains compliant with all federal and state emissions regulations in the United States. :

Air Quality Compliance Testing - TCS provides comprehensive emissions testing services employing Code of Federal (CFR) test methodologies, with Qualified Stack Testing Individuals (QSTI) having more than 20 years of experience in the emissions testing field.

PM Services - TCS employs a skilled staff to help customers develop the needed preventive maintenance programs to meet compliance as well as maximize run time on their equipment. We employ Caterpillar (CAT), Waukesha, and Ariel certified technicians that will perform the needed PM on all types of equipment. TCS offers OEM overhaul services on compressor packages and is a supplier for multiple types of parts to service compressor station equipment.

Catalyst Services - TCS offers a full line of catalyst services including annual cleaning of elements or replacement services. We offer pickup and delivery services for our customer owned catalyst elements that need cleaning services at no extra cost, these items can be returned in a 24 hour time frame if shop capacity is available. Our product line offers new replacement elements and catalyst housing to fit most applications. Most parts sold by TCS offer installation services for additional fees.

Exhaust Insulation - TCS provides custom designed exhaust insulation services. Our insulation is fully engineered to be an exact fit for the customer's application. Each wrap is designed to be replaceable with part numbers and full design drawings for each application. TCS offers installation services for its products as well.

Engine Tuning - Our company employs qualified personnel and tooling to properly tune compressor packages to meet customer permit limits. TCS offers catalyst cleaning and replacement services for all types of catalyst elements on low emission and rich burn applications.

4. CUSTOMER AND STAKEHOLDER

Customers are external stakeholders because even though they affect the day to day running of the business, they do not work within the business. Customers have an interest in Tesco because they want to buy their products (food, clothing, electronics etc.) and services (banking, mobile, club card etc.) that are a good quality and a reasonable price

Some of the customers of TCS are :

HSBC Bank
Zee Entertainment
Ben ATM Systems
Mercedes-Benz
Suzuki
Viacom entertainment
T-series
ICICI Bank
Bank of America
Reserve Bank
Johnson and johnsons
American Management Systems
Russian Navy
Andrews Air Force Base
Bank of AmericaAvis Rent A automotive
Berman William Blake Associates
Brookhaven National science laboratory.
Defense provision Agency
Daimler Mercedes-Benz
Department of Energy
Deutsche Bank
HP
Health and Hospital Corporation of latest House of York

HSASC
IBM Corporation
PeopleSoft
Kirlin Securities
Lockheed Martin
U.S. Navy
New York town Board of Education
Pencom Systems opposition.
Svenska Handelsbanken, U.S. Navy, Russian Army.

5. SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH GREEN STRATEGY

Disability Allowance is a means-tested payment. To get the allowance your total assessed means must be below a certain amount. The main items that count as means are:

Cash income that you or your spouse, civil partner or cohabitant may have. More information is available in our document about cash income not included in the means test.

Capital, for example, the value of savings, investments, shares or any property you may have (other than your own home). However, the first \$50,000 of any capital you have is not taken into account. More information is available in our document about capital and social welfare payments.

Maintenance paid to you. More information is available in our document about how maintenance is assessed as means.

At the age of 29, Jamsetji Tata worked in his father's company. In 1869 with Rs.21,000 capital, he founded a trading company. Further he bought a bankrupt oil mill at Chinchpokli and converted it into a cotton mill, under the name Alexandra Mill which he sold in profit after 2 years. In 1874, he set up another cotton mill at Nagpur named as Empress Mill. He dreamed of achieving 4 goals, setting up an iron and steel company, a unique hotel, a world-class learning institution and a hydro-electric plant. During his lifetime, in 1903, the Taj Mahal Hotel at Colaba waterfront was opened making it the first hotel with electricity in India. After Jamsetji's death, his older son Dorabji Tata became the Chairman in 1904. Sir Dorab established the Tata Iron and Steel company, now known as Tata Steel in 1907.

6. HR HIRING AND TRAINING STRATEGY

TCS is a Fortune five hundred company whose main service is in IT business. Today it's the leading firm on the market providing a lot of IT solutions to its customers and stakeholders. The business scope of TCS starts from Telecommunication, Banking, Financing, selling to producing. Like most international corporations, TCS features a matrix structure. Its various branches across the world work together to reach the organization's strategic aims. Thus, performance management in TCS has 2 totally different management strategies for normal staff and contractors or middleman. And HR is the main and every effective decision and hiring of all candidates are decided by the Centralized HR department.

At TCS Limited, they truly trust that the activities of the association and its locale are high reliant. It is through steady and cooperative communications with the outside partners that the Company endeavors to end up a resource for the networks where it works. With a little commitment as gift, they help uncommon necessities young ladies relationship in their central goal to convey groundbreaking help to the people who required it the most. As a productive accomplice in the network, TCS has been endeavor solid activity to understand its social duty targets, along these lines building an incentive for its clients and network. The TCS likewise gives money related and equipment backing to a few different exercises, for example, setting up another school Medical camp to address locale explicit medicinal issues, legitimate sanitation offices for young ladies and so on, and furthermore they bolster various activities concentrated on destroying absence of education and enabling individuals.

7. ANALYSIS

Performance of the TCS Company: The Management is satisfied to educate the investors that following a time of 5 years, the Company has posted a Net Profit after Tax (called Total Comprehensive Income under the Indian Accounting Standards informed by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs) of Rs.95.09 crores for the financial year 2016-17. On the operational front, the Company tried noteworthy endeavors amid the year towards enhancing operational execution over its center organizations and is completely equipped to advance on its development desires. The push in the coming years, beginning from FY 2017-18, isn't just to fortify the organization's situation in picked regions yet, in addition, to get energy and develop.

Business Overview: The association has an exhaustive game plan of IP based programming game plans, joined with a broad assortment of IT Services to address the dynamic necessities of an arrangement of industry verticals including Banking, Insurance, Capital Markets, Asset and Wealth organization (BFSI). They similarly give answers for various verticals, for instance, Government, Manufacturing, Distribution, Telecom, and Healthcare. The business activities of the Company are broadly isolated into two classes, viz. IT Solutions and

Transaction Services IT Solutions business contains programming things and IT enabled organizations while the trade organizations include BPO and KPO organizations. The association has a fair thing portfolio and has a prevalent proximity in rapidly creating rising economies. The thing business of the association has a wide base with more than 1000 powerful customers who are alluringly using the association's things. The association has spread crosswise over 50 countries across more than six operational geologies, viz. South Asia, Asia Pacific (APAC), Middle East and Africa, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Western Europe (WE) and North America (US). The TCS business is, all things considered, isolated into Emerging Markets and Developed Markets.

Strengths

- The barriers to market entry can be solved.
- Monetary assistance is provided in the company.
- A skilled workforce is available in the company.
- TCS reduced labor costs.
- They can maintain existing distribution and sales networks.
- TCS provide unique products.

Weaknesses

Future productivity.

High investments in research and development.

Opportunities

TCS is the multinational Indian economy.

Growth rates and profitability.

Venture capital.

Income level is at a constant increase.

Threats

Price changes.

Increase in labor costs.

Growing competition and lower profitability.

8. TOP COMPETITORS

HCL Technologies

- Market cap. 21,337.8 Cr

MphasiS Ltd.

- Market cap. 11,381.60 Cr

Tech Mahindra.

- Market cap. 12,500.20 Cr

Wipro.

- Market cap. 1570.05 Cr

Infosys.

- Market cap. 34,018.11 Cr

9. FINANCE

Absolute Returns for last 5 financial years:

Past performance may or may not be sustained in future.

10. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER INNOVATIONS

- Rethink your high-level business strategy

- Collaborate with more technology-related industries and companies.
- Eliminates projects and processes that don't work
- Recognize and protect Entrepreneur's

11. CONCLUSIONS

Historically, TCS has focused on the creation of multimedia and creativity software products, however, through exploration, innovation, and exploitation the company has evolved into a broad-based Internet application. While not entirely without, TCS enjoys a very limited number of competitors with product and service lines that and closely mirror its own The company will need to manage explosive growth without sacrificing its positive company culture and reputation for meeting the needs of consumers by delivering quality services and products. TCS business strategies are discussed as per the guidelines given in Company analysis case study methodology.

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